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Artificial Intelligence-Based Adaptive Learning: A Tool for Effective Teaching and Learning at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

Artificial intelligent in educational classrooms for effective instructions; opened up new possibilities for students' and teachers in teaching and learning process at Secondary School level of education in Nigeria. This paper explores the effective teaching and learning at secondary school level of education in Nigeria, using artificial intelligence-based adaptive learning: by determining adaptive learning experiences to learners, promoting teaching and learning as well as curriculum development. Artificial Intelligence has become an indispensable tool for teaching and learning, offering teachers the means to adapt, engage, and personalize learning experiences for students. The researchers delve into pivotal role of AI-based adaptive learning platform in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes within instructional settings that aids to fill the gaps in education.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Ai-based adaptive learning, AI at secondary school level.

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) usage contributes to the transformation of the learning process towards a student-centered learning environment (Hafa, Moubtassim, 2021). Thus, to determine the benefits of AI-based learning platform on students, it is crucial to look into students' engagement in using AI technology in their learning practice. This study will explore the effectiveness of AI-based adaptive learning platforms on teaching and learning practices at secondary school level of education; traditional classroom settings often struggle to address the individual needs and learning pace of students due to large class sizes and limited resources. The implementation of AI-based adaptive learning platforms has the potential to revolutionize education in Nigeria, enhancing student engagement, motivation, and ultimately, their academic performance. Reports from UNESCO (Miao et al., 2021) and OECD (2021) provide evidence of the potential of AI to improve education by automating various aspects of teaching (e.g., administrative tasks, assessment, evaluation), personalizing learning (e.g., intelligent tutoring systems), and making available new tools (e.g., virtual reality, augmented reality).

Over the last decade, researchers have examined the use of AI in teaching and learning for different purposes. For example, quite a few researchers examined the use of AI applications such as intelligent tutoring systems, virtual reality, and teaching evaluation (Chassignol et al., 2018; Gerard et al., 2015; Guan et al., 2020; Parsia et al., 2020; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Zhai et al., 2020), as well as the use of more general pedagogical methods (game based learning, collaborative learning) in teaching and learning in various contexts and disciplines (Bozkurt et al., 2021; Feng & Law, 2021; ZawackiRichter et al., 2019). In all these practices, Artificial intelligence deployed to improves teaching and learning at secondary school level of education in Nigeria; for effective global practices of instructions.

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What is Concept of Artificial intelligence?

John McCarthy introduced the term Artificial Intelligence in the 1950s, defining it as “the science and engineering of making intelligent machines”. Since then, the field has evolved and so has the definition of AI. Currently, there is no single universal definition of AI. This is partially due to the rapid development of the field, but also because researchers outside of computer science, in the areas of education, healthcare, philosophy, economics, and arts have taken a great interest in AI and its application. Each of these research fields has modified the term AI to its own needs and uses, and this interdisciplinary nature of AI makes it difficult to establish a consensus about what AI is.

Popenici and Kerr (2017), who define AI as “computing systems that are able to engage in human-like processes such as learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correcting and use of data for complex processing tasks” Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be defined as a system that has been designed to interact with the world in difference ways we may think of as human and intelligent. The line of, Ample data, cheap computing and AI algorithms mean technology can learn very quickly. The transformative power of AI cuts across all sectors, including education (UNESCO, 2019). AI will change learning, teaching, and educational classrooms situation. The speed of technological change will be very fast, and it will create high level to transform educational practices, institutions, and policies." Therefore, provision of AI-based working environment promotes learning, teaching, education and curriculum development as well as policy development.

Artificial Intelligence as an Adaptive Learning Facility in Educational Classrooms at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

On January 1st, 1997, the International Artificial Intelligence in Education Society (AIED) was established. By hosting the International Journal of AI in Education (IJAIED) and AIED conference series, it brings researchers together. There are four main areas of AIED in institutional and administrative services, academic support services, and services that promote learning, including profiling and prediction, assessment and evaluation, adaptive systems, personalization, and intelligent tutoring systems. The application of AI is both inventive and derived. A new technology called artificial intelligence has begun to alter educational resources and curriculum organizations. The ideal educational practice in the sphere of education requires the presence of teachers. The employment of teachers, who are vital to the educational system, is altered by the development of artificial intelligence. The AI primarily employs deep learning, machine learning, and advanced analytics to track a specific person's relative speed to other people.

AI is capable of customizing the academic curriculum. With the use of AI-Based adaptive learning platform, worldwide classrooms can accommodate students who have hearing or vision impairments. Students who are ill and unable to attend class can also benefit from this. Additionally, AI aids in providing advice on how to close learning gaps. Makes learning easier and instructions effective (Pujari, 2022). AI may also be used for admissions and enrolment procedures, while its full potential it still developing. AI can aid students in their home study habits and exam readings. Future AI will be able to respond to various learning styles, the like of convergent, divergent, impulsive and flexible learning styles, among others to mentioned, but a few to achieve the objectives.

Application of AI as a Learning Partner in Educational Classroom At Secondary School level of Education

AI technologies have brought a paradigm shift in educational classrooms, creating possibilities for personalized learning, data-driven decision-making, and innovative pedagogical approaches (Oliveira, et al., 2019, Grimus, 2020). AI-based adaptive learning platforms have been implemented in various regions worldwide, showcasing their effectiveness in improving students learning, skills and experiences. Therefore, the most common AI-enabled educational applications, and one none AI-enabled application. Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) are an AI application as they provide personalized and adaptive instruction to learners. ITS take on the role of a human tutor, by offering guidance, feedback, and support to learners; It does so, using AI techniques to capture learner’s strengths, weaknesses, and progress. By adapting the learning content, difficulty level, and feedback, to these learning traits of each individual user, the learning experience is then optimized.

Application of AI as a Learning Material in Educational Classroom at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

The integration of AI in educational classrooms has potential for optimizing administrative processes, providing instructional resources, yielding efficiency and cost-effectiveness, as evidenced by scholarly research (Klutka et al., 2018). AI-based adaptive learning platforms can also leverage various learning resources, such as interactive videos, simulations, and gamified elements, to create engaging and immersive learning experiences. AI can be used as a tool by teachers to facilitate the teaching and learning design or to support teachers' scaffolding strategies and to track students' learning progress and

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outcomes (Chounta et.al., 2021; Lindner & Romeiki 2019). The advancement of educational technology and digital platforms such as educational learning applications, Learning Management Systems (LMS) and virtual classrooms can be utilized to assist in the teaching and learning of a language more effectively. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) usage contributes to the transformation of the learning process towards a student-centered environment (Hafa, Moubtassim, 2021). Online Instructional materials that are associated with AI tools and applications; used by students and teachers such as Quizizz, Kahoot, and Google Classroom.

Challenges of AI Technology at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

Despite the enormous opportunities AI presents, there may also be some possible challenges. AI has the potential to be either the greatest and friendly evil for humanity. The development of AI applications in educational classrooms has new ethical concerns and risks that could help teaching and learning process. Some of the challenges include:

1. Lack of adequate access to computers and internet connection, therefore technology use is not feasible in classrooms;
2. Need for access to professional development on new technologies like AI;
3. Need for full administrative and peer support on technology integration, result by inadequate technical support;
4. Lack of an understanding of the usefulness and experience of digital technologies (Aduwa-ogiegbaen, 2014; johnson et al., 2016).

Benefits of AI Technology at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

AI can affect teaching and learning. AI can be used to shape the education and instructional process, through for example, digital assistants which support the teacher in teaching in the classroom. AI can undertake administrative tasks, freeing teachers for more time supporting learners. In the school context, there could also be AI-based learning data analysis (Learning Analytics), AI-based individualized learning offers (Adaptive Learning) or AI-based assessment systems (mmb Institut, 2020). despite their specific design, these applications would change learning and instructional process as well students' development.

Another impact for students in educational classroom is that the transformative power of AI promises profound changes in instructional strategy and resources. AI improves changes in initial and continuing training for teachers and students in educational environment. Therefore, the AI-based tools for teaching and learning can be used in the classroom to improve the quality of the instructional delivery. Also, AI can address certain challenges or consequences of the increased use of technology in the classroom. AI technologies are organized in schools to prepare 'learners' for an AI-based working environment.

Therefore, the learning styles and behavioral patterns of students can be analyzed by AI-based adaptive learning systems, which can then offer them content, exercises, and tests that are specifically tailored to the students' needs. Additionally, teachers can track students' development more precisely and offer targeted help as required. AI-based adaptive learning is a growingly popular option for schools and universities throughout the world due to its potential to increase student engagement and outcomes. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools to customize server education and training for groups of learners is referred to as server customization education.

Conclusion

AI-based Adaptive learning have the potential to revolutionize the way education is delivered, administered, and researched, leading to more efficient and effective instructional experiences for students and teachers. While the impact of AI-based adaptive learning in educational classrooms, include personalized learning, adaptive assessments, improved student engagement, enhanced administrative processes, and research capabilities, there are also certain improvement in the quality of instructional process and provision of AI-based working environment for learners. In the 21st century academic era and beyond, AI-based adaptive learning platform remains a dynamic and transformative to education; shaping the future of learning.

Recommendations

On the bases of the above discussions, the following recommendations are made:

1. AI technology often address the individual needs and learning pace of students with limited resources.
2. Enhancement of student's engagement and their academic performance
3. Changing the learning and teaching of educational classrooms situation
4. AI technology aids in the provision onto fill the learning gaps

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